

The draft is a long summary of important results that help us understanding something about PFAs, some outcomes on dietary exposure, some hypothesis on metabolic pathways, also evidences on their interaction with biologic processes.

These compounds behave, like other POPs, as endocrine disruptors as they can modulate immunosystem response and interfere with lipids metabolism (as well as steroid hormones). They are a risk for our health and fixing a No Adverse Effect Level is a primary goal.

However it's not clear how data presented in Annex A, B, C, and all through the draft (transfer from feed to food, biomonitoring, epidemiological studies, etc..) have contributed to the implementation of PBPK model, and eventually to the proposal of the TWI.

Starting from some conclusions:

line 6471

This TWI should prevent that mother reach a body burden that results in levels....in milk that can be dangerous for breastfed infants.

Levels come from two studies, the German one and the Faroe Islands one, which correlate NOAEC serum levels at the age of 1 year and 5 years to inverse association with antibody titres for some diseases.

The TWI, in nutshell, is the result of these experiences and the PBPK model.

This model is made up of big data set, whose confidence is not discussed.

The data input for the model are supposed to be "the best fitting" ones to represent the complexity of several biological processes like transfer of Pfas from food to plasma/serum and to milk.

Surely they are, but Appendix M is quite hazy; I think that PFAs question is quite recent and data in our hands are often used, let's say forced, behind their value.

My contribution comes from analytical experience in lab activities.

As a lab technician, I suggest all the difficulties of dealing with rather new contaminants, whose knowledge is poor, lacking of technologies up to the aim.

ARPA labs have different equipments and ISPRA report 305/2019 shows a certain disomogeneity in analytical performances.

In surface waters, the easiest samples if compared to plasma or other biological matrix, few steps are needed before instrumental analysis; preconcentration (250 times and more) is the most important one, because of very low detection limits imposed by law; SPE (solid phase extraction) needs very well trained operators.

If samples are clean and you can skip some steps, you may have filtration problem, because perfluorocompounds are wide spread in lab materials, and blanks are challenging; in any case high resolution detectors are necessary and long experience with trace analysis.

In this regard, labs complain lack of Proficiency Test at very low concentration to prove and check their technical skill.

I think that growing interest in this matter led to an increase in PFAs analysis and a wide spread provision of data, some of which totally unreliable.

Results of monitoring plans don't come from statistic analysis of large amount of data, but are driven by limits of the law; PFOS is present in 50% and more of water samples under analysis, *because* Law limits are 10 times lower than for other compounds. Most of the difference is due to false positives.

Statistic approach is crucial to understand the extent of PFAS question, in order not to over or underestimate it; since the results are often < LOQ, the choice of LB or UB criterion makes the difference.

In surface water, PFAS are seldom or weakly bound, but in serum and plasma PFAs may be associated with albumin and other protein; I think various analytical problems can affect the result. Also milk analysis is a quite long

procedure, starting with precipitation of proteins and proceeding with similar steps.

In 2013 a group of researchers (Barbarossa et al.) has investigated Pfas level in human milk provided by primiparous mothers (PFOS ranges from 100 to 300 ng/l, higher concentration in primiparous mothers.. Correlation between blood Pfas and milk concentration have also been found...serum or plasma ?...

I think this line of research can be very promising.

Again, 27 ng/ml in 1 year child serum is consistent with data in milk?

For sure, informations on food consumption must be improved and FoodEx system will help to homogenize data.

Data in Annex A, like INRAN SCAL (2005-2006) are quite old and have been conceived for other aim.

The representativity of italian dietary is poor, both for number of families (1329) taken into account, and for composition of the sample.

Children under 3 years are quite ignored; breast feeding mothers are only 10 (but these categories are those for whom the WTI has been thought).

Emilia Romagna is represented with less than 100 families, living in the western region (RE), while people living in the coastal region where fish consumption is greater, have not been considered. (Further investigation in last years proved that farmed fish is healthier than caught fish, and in general wild animals are more contaminated than breed ones, owing to environmental pollution.) We know very little about what people do eat.

So, Goethe paradox says that knowledge is like a sphere, the more the knowledge, the more the surface touching the unknown.

In conclusion, I think that the proposal of a TWI is somehow ambitious, and pretty useless, at this early stage of investigation.